

ATTENTION TO YOUTH AND FORMATION OF INNOVATIVE THINKING IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. The article scientifically analyzes the issues of educating young people and paying attention to them, as well as the formation of innovative thinking in New Uzbekistan. Education, especially the education of a comprehensively developed personality, is an important process necessary not only for today, but also for our future. If the current young generation receives the right education, if it can understand the current reforms, the successes achieved will undoubtedly bear fruit in the future. Because only spiritually mature people can build a bright society. In the construction and development of civil society in our country today, it is necessary to educate a spiritually healthy generation, to form in them national traditions of morality. After all, it has been proven that the moral qualities of our people, practiced since ancient times, are the basis of our spirituality.

Keywords: youth, innovation, thinking, socio-spiritual needs, reforms, upbringing, education, national revival, national upsurge.

The large-scale reforms being implemented in the new Uzbekistan in all areas, first of all, are combined with the goal of satisfying not only the material, but also the social and spiritual needs of the population, and at the same time, literally educating people. with high spirituality. The role and importance of spiritual and moral institutions in the accelerated development of state social policy, the requirements for “further increasing the effectiveness of the national idea and ideological and educational work, which is one of the important factors in ensuring the effectiveness of reforms carried out in order to renew society and realize human interests” [1] proves it. Therefore, at the new stage of development of our country, which fully implements the concession from national revival to national uplift, the need to educate enlightened youth in society becomes apparent.

In his Message to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020, Respected President Sh. Mirziyoyev said: “In order to increase the knowledge and level of not only young people, but also members of our society as a whole, first of all, knowledge and high spirituality are necessary. Where there is no knowledge, there will be backwardness, ignorance and, of course, delusion. As the sages of the East say: “The greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, the greatest inheritance is a good education, and the greatest poverty is ignorance!” - emphasizes [2].

Raising a person who is perfect in all respects is the eternal dream of humanity, and our ancestors were looking for ways and rules on how to teach education and culture to the younger generation and lead them to perfection. As a result of these studies, the foundations of national education were formed.

The worldview of the youth of our country is also becoming the object of spiritual and ideological influence. “The education of the younger generation,” said the head of state, “has

always been important and relevant.” But in the 21st century in which we live, this question really becomes a matter of life and death” [3, p. 504-505]. Because “at present, on a global scale, merciless competition, contradictions and conflicts are intensifying” [3, p. 505.] Therefore, the issue of protecting the worldview of young men and women from spiritual manipulation is interpreted as a generally significant task; in connection with this, the works were turned into a separate direction of spiritual and educational activity. However, a rapidly changing reality requires the search for new and more effective ways to protect the consciousness and worldview of young people. That is why they believe that “we will be able to achieve the goals we have set for ourselves only if we can educate smart and highly spiritual people; issues of prosperity and development will be resolved in our country” [3, p.81].

In order to develop a healthy spiritual need in our youth, we must give them sufficient knowledge and understanding of our national and cultural history. As our great scholars have noted, the way to feed an individual, and ultimately society, from the source of enlightenment is to immerse the individual in spirituality and enlightenment. The only way to protect a person and society from various misfortunes is to heal the soul and make it healthy. Of course, for this it is necessary to form high spirituality in the hearts of young people. Because the highest task of beauty is to serve the development of spiritual wealth and moral purity in people [5, p.208].

“One of our great thinkers, Aristotle, said: “You cannot act in public life without possessing certain moral qualities, for example, being a worthy person” [6, p.102].

The peoples of Central Asia have a rich tradition in the field of ethics. Moral ideas are expressed in the religious and moral book “Avesta”, ancient Turkish writings and other written sources. In addition, morality is given a wide place in pannonas, trainings and etiquettes, folk pedagogy, religious and philosophical treatises, and the heritage of scientists widespread among the Uzbek people.

“Kabusnama” by Kaykovus, “Kutadgu Bilig” by Yusuf Khos Hajib, “Hibat ul-Hakaiq” by Ahmed Yungnaki, “Gulistan” and “Boston” by Saadi, “Bakhoristan” by A. Jami, “Mahbub ul-Kulub” by A. Navoi, Works by Abdullah Avloni's "Turkish Gulistan or Morality" is moral, didactic and philosophical in nature, and all of them glorify human virtues.

“In order not to make a mistake in the matter of family education,” our respected head of state emphasizes elsewhere, “first of all, it would be important to build a spiritual climate in every home based on mutual respect, ethics and human relations” [7, p. 55] .

A. Avloni, the founder of the development of pedagogical ideas, defines ethics as follows: “This is a science that calls people to good and protects them from evil. A book that explains, with the help of evidence and examples, the good of good behavior and the evil of bad behavior is called ethics” [8, 11 p.].

Abdullah Avlani shows that the conditions, environment and people in which he lives have a big role in raising a child, and he does not ignore family and school conditions in this area. The author believes that it is necessary to educate the body in order to have a healthy spirit, good morals and knowledge: “A healthy and strong body is the most necessary thing for a person. Because in order to read, teach, study and teach, a person needs strength and a healthy body” [8, p. 14]. In this place, Abdullah Avloni teaches parents that along with raising children, great attention should be paid to their health. Speaking about the good qualities of a person, he expresses his thoughts in such poetic lines:

If you speak, say good words
Otherwise, it is better to remain silent.
Think positive, think
Otherwise, it's better to be dumb.
If you work, do a good deed
Otherwise your idleness is good [p. 8, 11].

A spiritually perfect person is one who follows the unity of reason and virtue. Virtue is the best quality a person can acquire. As our thinkers say, harmony of heart and mind is necessary for the development of high human qualities in people. Because where the heart and mind are united, there is a desire for development, goodness, kindness and beauty. Perfect human education, especially the formation in the hearts of young people of the qualities of kindness, virtue, love for the nation and the Motherland, does not happen by itself. To do this, it is necessary not only to acquaint them with the spiritual and educational works of our great scientists, written in the pandnoma style, but also to organize many meaningful events, conversations and dialogues on various topics, and excursions to the historical places of our country. .

The modern high development of science, technology, technology and production automatically puts new social demands on the agenda. Among these social needs of society, the force that drives the development of industries based on it is important - the training of qualified personnel, the improvement of the system aimed at this goal. The need for training qualified personnel depends on the social, economic and cultural development of society, the emergence of new directions, specializations, the need to train personnel in them, and the formation of the need for consistent improvement of professional knowledge and skills. and the skills of professionals in a changing, rapidly changing era. In addition, there is a growing demand for specialists who can cope with the fierce competition in the labor market. In modern conditions, a special place in providing the social, economic and cultural sphere with qualified personnel is occupied by a system of continuous education with a carefully thought-out mechanism, in particular the level of a higher educational institution [8, p. 388-391].]

As mentioned above, the rapidly developing era poses the task of professionals to be prepared for fundamental changes, to shape and develop themselves from a social and professional point of view, keeping up with the times.

The high-quality organization of the educational process in higher educational institutions makes a great contribution to the ability of specialists to fully satisfy this demand. If deep ideas about the meaning and essence of these principles and values are formed in the family, there is no doubt that serious positive changes will occur in the consciousness of young people, their education, worldview and lifestyle. In addition, an innovative approach to improving the system for forming the ideological and political culture of youth in the family acquires important social significance in the spiritual, moral, educational development of society. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated that "... the noblest dreams and goals of every family in our country are first of all manifested and realized in the image of its children" [4], and his thoughts are more than ever responsible for the upbringing of the younger generation and demands not to be indifferent.

Today, when the formation of ideological and political culture in the minds of young people, the development of ideological immunity is recognized as a social task, especially in the family, it is necessary to scientifically substantiate an innovative approach to improving

the system of Formation of ideological and political culture of youth as a pedagogical task, to reveal the essence of its content and construction, as well as for young people to learn selected data that reveals the content and specific features of the values that determine the level of an innovative approach to improving the system for forming the ideological and political culture of youth in the family, studying the psychological and pedagogical aspects of this innovative approach, identifying factors, conditions and requirements, developing acceptable models and experimenting with its effectiveness to determine on the basis of the test, develop scientific, pedagogical and methodological recommendations that will help him instill in the hearts of the younger generation high human qualities, such as national pride, national identity, national consciousness, through teaching the ideas of patriotism, the idea of progress, national peace, young people fall into an ideological gap in order to prevent them from staying, the study and research of some socio-spiritual, moral aspects of ideological and political culture as a special subject of research is one of the pressing problems of our time [9, p. 317-319].

At a time when science, technology, technology is developing, the innovative education system is widely used, the processes of globalization and acceleration are rapidly entering, our youth are sufficiently aware of scientific and technical achievements, historical events and phenomena, and the development of social life. influences the education and upbringing of youth. In a word, today's development and progress have their own demands on our parents, including not wasting time and saving, the lives and spiritual world of our children today. It is recognized that the struggle of ideas and competition of ideologies continues continuously and regularly, they all look for a way to the mind and subconscious layers of a person, his heart and soul, and it is recognized that the ideology that occupies the spiritual life of people will win. In this struggle, with the hand of one force or another increasingly dominant in geopolitics, it is said that it becomes dependent on the sphere of ideology and spirituality. Therefore, we protect our youth from spiritual decay and poverty, and our ideological opponents promote immorality as personal freedom [10, 3-4 pp.], promiscuity as the triumph of democracy and the desire to preserve identity, spirituality and national pride. ... we must be able to accept what is interpreted as clinging to the old, stifling freedom, lack of democracy.

That is why, if we seriously approach the process of forming the ideological and political culture of young people from the family, we must ensure the social interests of the family, create a healthy psychological environment in the family, and increase the legal literacy of the family. , enrich the knowledge of young people about political consciousness and political thinking, increase their political knowledge, general and aesthetic education., education of hard work, instilling a national idea, love for the Motherland, true friendship, strong faith, faith, sophistication. , moral culture, etc. This requires focusing on making yesterday and tomorrow better than today. One of the most pressing life tasks today is to strengthen the activities of public organizations "Family, neighborhood and educational institutions" in order to educate an ideologically and politically developed personality, improve the political culture of young people and their activity in society. political life of society. In this regard, educational psychologists, like every member of society, have a great responsibility. After all, education is not only the work of parents or teachers, but also the work of creative people who care about their future and strive for great goals.

It should be noted that in the conditions of modern globalization, it is necessary to radically improve the conditions in preschool and primary educational institutions for the

comprehensive intellectual, aesthetic and physical development of children, and seriously expand the coverage of children in preschool institutions. education and ensuring its convenience, attention should be paid to improving the qualifications of teachers and specialists. In particular, a radical improvement in the quality of general secondary education requires in-depth study of other important and popular subjects, such as foreign languages, computer science, mathematics, physics, chemistry and biology.

So, in conclusion, we can state that without raising the morale of children and students in the family, it is impossible to raise the morale of people and society. Raising a spiritually mature and physically healthy generation is one of the main principles of our national ideology, therefore the moral education of children should become our daily work. We think that this will have a positive impact on the development of our country and will contribute to the creation of a morally healthy and strong society.

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